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"URBAN LIVING"

The hustle and bustle of the city
Makes people move in and settle quickly,
Although cost of living is very high,
Ev'rything's always ready and close by
Too many leisure spots to go to,
Shop until you drop if you want to do,
Eating can be on the streets or fancy,
Choose for as long as you will be happy,
From high-rise buildings and long skyways
To housing, people are there anyways,
Indifferent and nonchalant they are,
Looking like they are just an avatar
Life in the city is not this easy,
It is hard but may seem easy-breezy.